

USED IN LESSON PROCESSES EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation: In this article, the opinions about the improvement of the quality and effectiveness of the interactive methods in the lesson processes organized in the educational institutions and the skills required of the teacher to interest the student in the lesson are described.

Key words: education, quality of education, interactive methods, activity, assignment, pedagogue, technology, mastering.

The teacher organizes the educational process using various educational methods. "Educational method is the method of work used by the teacher to increase the knowledge, skills and abilities of students, to form their worldview, and to develop their mastery abilities." The method is used in the practical training through methods appropriate to its essence. "...the principles of education and training under certain conditions expand their sphere of influence, have a strong influence on education and training. In such a case, we use some principle as a method, or in other words, a principle becomes a method."

The educational process has a two-way character: the teacher teaches, the student learns. Naturally, there is a certain goal in the activity of both the teacher and the

student. The main goal of a teacher's activity is to provide education, to develop the ability to understand, to develop the culture of feeling, moral concepts, to make him a spiritually pure person. The main goal of the student's activity is to fulfill the teacher's task and master the knowledge given in the educational process. A student, especially a young student, may not understand the essence of the purpose of the teacher's work, may not be able to fully imagine the process of education and upbringing. But he knows and feels that he has to fulfill his teacher's task.

By completing one or another task of the teacher, the student feels that his knowledge is increasing and cognitive activity is developing, but he does not feel that he is mastering the method of the subject he is studying. Accordingly, in the process of education, the teacher should create cognitive activity in students, teach them ways to consciously and deeply accept literary material, and use these ways to perform independent tasks. Today, the rapid development of the fields of science, technology and production requires raising the quality of education in all educational institutions to a new level in terms of content. This, in turn, imposes higher responsibilities and duties on each system employee, especially teachers. After all, there is one undeniable fact - all the efforts made will eventually show their results through the work of the teacher. Therefore, pedagogues are required to work conscientiously, to be responsible for our bright future, and to respond appropriately to the high attention shown. "What is the difference between a good teacher and a great teacher? A good teacher develops his student's abilities to the limit. A great teacher can see this limit at a glance" - said the German philosopher Johann Goethe. This fact is reflected in a quality lesson that plays a key role in our children's in-depth knowledge acquisition.

It is known that one of the urgent issues of today is to raise the young generation to be a perfect person, highly spiritual, patriotic, creative and active in all aspects. The

performance of these tasks is mainly assigned to the subject of mother tongue and literature in general secondary education.

In particular, teaching using advanced pedagogical technologies motivates students to thirst for knowledge, inquisitiveness, resourcefulness.

The importance of every lesson is great in raising students to be mature and well-rounded people in all respects. If the teacher uses different methods and techniques in the lesson, the student's attitude to the lesson will be good. If every pedagogue teaches a similar method, educational

If games are organized based on scientific principles, they will acquire pedagogical skills that meet the requirements of the times. After all, it is necessary for students to receive not only knowledge, but also education from the teacher during the lesson. As the first President I.A. Karimov noted, "We need not graduates, but people who have received school education."

The careful use of various methods in the course of the lesson ensures the continued cooperation of the teacher and students. At the same time, this cooperation forms a sincere relationship between the teacher and the student. Also, interactive methods used correctly with the teacher's creativity save students from the same continuous boring environment and make them a participant in learning theoretical information about the subject.

turns Taking into account that the teacher works more with the group during the lecture sessions, recommending students to work with the "BBB" graphic organizer or the "Insert" graphic organizer based on the lecture itself divided them into the topic. creates warm relations. In essence, innovative, modular, collaborative, interactive, problem-based, distance, computer, project, individual, programmatic,

developmental, differentiated and independent education, as well as the same teaching process in the educational system of game technologies , of being boring prevention, on the contrary, serves to create the necessary conditions for it to be interesting and active. It is important for school teachers to be aware of the essence of these educational technologies, to be able to use them effectively in their activities, every education in the educational process.

Pedagogical activity is a complexly organized system of a number of activities: the most important of them is the activity of the teacher who teaches directly.

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